

soil in early Aug after plots were thoroughly puddled. Rice was harvested in early Dec.

Growth and development of rice and fish with and without supplemental feed at the Operational Research Project, Pandua, West Bengal, India.

Character	Without fish		With fish
	Control	Without feed	With feed
<i>Randhunipagal</i>			
Plant height (cm)	136	134	127
Effective tillers/plant	14	10	11
Panicle length (cm)	21	21	21
Grains/panicle	106	106	121
Grain sterility (%)	11	10	10
<i>Singhi and Magur</i>			
Survival (%)	–	75	72
Increase in length (mm)	–	6	25
Increase in weight (g)	–	17	41

Releasing air-breathing fingerlings in the paddy field.

Soil was a clay loam with pH from 5.9 to 6.2. Farmyard manure at 9 t/ha was applied to all plots. Two plants spaced 20 × 20 cm were transplanted in each hill. Normal cultivation methods were practiced and water level was maintained at 8-10 cm.

Ten plants for analysis were randomly selected from each treatment and uprooted at harvest. Growth and yield data for 10 randomly selected fishes from each of treatments 2 and 3 also were recorded at harvest (see table, figure).

Rice grown with the air-breathing fish yielded more than the control, and the plots with supplemental feed produced more (see table). Plots with supplemental feed also yielded the heaviest and longest fish. Straw yield was lower in treatments 2 and 3 because of reduced plant height. □

Effect of sowing date on growth and performance of six rice varieties in western Turkey

M. Chaudhry, Principal Government College, Garhi Dopatta (A. K.), Pakistan

We studied the effect of different sowing dates on duration and yield of rice varieties and the efficacy of rice as a 2d crop after wheat or barley. Six rice varieties were sown on 7 dates at 10-d intervals from 2 Apr to 1 Jun in 1980 and 1981 in Izmir. Seedlings were transplanted at 4-

or 5-leaf stage at 10- × 30-cm spacing in 3 replications.

The highest average grain yield (8.2 t/ha) was from the second sowing, and the lowest (5.4 t/ha) was from the last sowing (see table). Calrose gave the highest average yield (9.1 t/ha) and Labelle yielded lowest (5.1 t/ha). The first sowing had the longest average duration (134 d) and the 6th sowing had the shortest (95 d). Labelle had the longest duration (121 d) and Krasnodorsky was earliest (98 d). There was a significant sowing date × variety effect on yield and duration (see table).

We concluded that in western Turkey,

- early seeding produces higher grain yield,
- short-grained Calrose and high quality varieties Kashmir Basmati and Labelle will grow and yield well if seeded in Apr,
- second crop transplanted rice (after 15 Jun) is possible after wheat or barley,
- delayed sowing generally decreases yield, and
- late sowing reduces grain yield more for short-duration varieties (Krasnodorsky and Maratelli) than for medium-duration varieties (Gritna). □

Effect of sowing date on days to heading (DH) and yield (Y) of six rices in western Turkey.

Sowing date ^a	Kashmir Basmati		Calrose		Gritna		Krasnodorsky		Labelle		Maratelli		Av	
	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH	Y (t/ha)	DH
1	8.7	138	11.4	147	6.0	127	6.3	122	6.4	141	5.8	126	7.4	134
2	9.1	128	13.0	137	6.2	116	7.2	110	6.2	130	7.4	113	8.2	122
3	7.3	120	8.7	127	5.8	109	5.8	102	5.2	126	6.7	105	6.6	115
4	7.5	113	8.6	119	5.3	101	5.4	95	5.0	121	6.2	98	6.3	108
5	8.0	105	8.6	111	5.9	94	5.4	86	4.9	113	6.2	92	6.5	100
6	6.5	98	7.5	102	5.3	91	4.5	84	4.3	107	4.8	88	5.5	95
7	6.2	101	6.0	97	6.0	100	5.0	87	3.9	107	5.2	86	5.4	96
Av	7.6	115	9.1	120	5.8	106	5.7	98	5.1	121	6.0	101		

LSD: (5%) Yield: Variety: 1.7 Sowing date: 1.7
DH: " : 4.3 " : 4.5

^a 2 Apr to 1 Jun at 10-d intervals.